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EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE AMONG THE TEACHERS OF SPECIAL NEEDS CHILDREN: A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW

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Abstract

This systematic review article is based on the previous literature and aims to explore the importance of emotional intelligence among teachers of special needs children. The current study has abstracted the 520 articles of EI, and further, these have been filtered, and 35 more relevant and suitable as per the study aim have been included in this systematic review. Random sampling has been used, and data has been collected from Google Scholar, PubMed, MDPI, and Science Direct. The literature matrix has been used to get the main findings. It has been found that EI is critical for teachers of special needs children to understand the behaviour of the student, manage their attitude and enhance their performance. The current study has found that there is a great need for training for special education children related to utilizing the EI because they are more stressed to teach in the special education sector compared to other educational institutes. The current study is limited to EI among special needs children and secondary sources. Future studies can be made through primary data collection, and the implications of the current review are effective in enhancing teachers of special education performance and EI for a better workplace.

Keywords: Emotional Intelligence, Teachers of Special Needs Children, Special Education, Systematic Review, Special Education teachers

Introduction

When it comes to building human capital, education is one of the most important factors available to shape human behaviour and educate them. Education gives people a way that they need to realize their life challenges and fulfil their potential. So, one of a nation's greatest assets lies in its educational system. These structures may shape a country's future for the better or worse (Gershon & Pellitteri, 2018). Elementary and secondary schooling in special education is crucial, and it provides the groundwork for further study. Special education's formal mode serves various purposes, one of which is to instil Emotional Intelligence in the teachers and students. One's full psychological potential may be realized via the development of Emotional Intelligence. The country's future prosperity and cultural advancement are seen in special education. It is believed that with sufficient investment in this sector, the country may become a developed nation by supporting special people (Sánchez-Álvarez et al., 2020).

Sabie et al. (2020) work suggests that a person's capacity to cope with environmental requirements and conflicts is strongly tied to the competencies closely associated with Emotional Intelligence. Considering this, it can be said that a person's level of Emotional Intelligence is a significant indicator of how good he will do in a special school and the workplace. According to Bower et al (2018), Emotional Intelligence is a subset of social Intelligence that requires a person to be attuned to and in control of their own emotions and those of others. Further, they broke down Emotional Intelligence (EI) into four sub-concepts: controlling and regulating emotions, comprehending and reasoning about emotions, integrating foundational emotional experiences and recognizing and assessing emotions.

The literature on both kinds of EI has indicated that teaching in special education is more difficult than in the normal education system because special education teachers

face the most problematic and worst situations. So, teachers of special needs children have a greater risk of experiencing stress (Mavilidi et al., 2021). Furthermore, the curriculum must be covered, lines of communication with parents and administration should be established, planned field excursions, and encouraged the professional growth of special education teachers to manage these issues. In this way, special education teachers are responsible for the tasks above and numerous papers and assignments sent down from the government and department heads (Namyssova et al., 2019).

The special education system places a great demand on teachers' time and resources. Teachers need the skills of motivation, perseverance in the face of frustration, impulse control, delay of gratification, and emotional regulation to handle such stress. Teachers of special needs children often find themselves in the middle of tense circumstances (Hughes & Davidson, 2020). Therefore, it's vital to cultivate and improve their emotional skills. Teachers in the special education sector who are well-versed in emotional Intelligence can better understand their connections with their pupils. Emotional intelligence capacity may be defined as the ability to pay attention, persist, manage impulses, freely communicate, think things through, make deliberate judgments, overcome difficulties, and strive for achievement (MacIntyre et al., 2020).

Additionally, the level of Emotional Intelligence a teacher has is often considered the most reliable indicator of that person's effectiveness in the classroom. Instructors should work on mastering their feelings, ideas, and convictions. Instilling such talents in teachers may help them become better educators (Mérida-López et al., 2020). According to Varea et al. (2021), educators may boost students' and colleagues' reflexivity, solidarity, and sensitivity via the expression of emotional identity. Further, they

elaborated that emotionally intelligent people can overcome obstacles by developing an awareness of and a facility with their own emotions. They tend to move up the corporate ladder faster than those with lower IQs in the emotional domain.

The transition from secondary school to postsecondary education is a watershed moment for students because it ushers in a whole new world of possibilities. To be successful, teachers at this level must help their students develop the skills necessary to succeed in the workforce (Malik, 2018). The role of the teacher has evolved to become more important as he or she provides guidance, guides, and motivates students to further their careers, but EI remains a largely underappreciated component of effective education (Reeve & Shin, 2020). Encouraging learning, however, includes more than just imparting knowledge; it also entails calming students' nerves and anxieties, and it gives lecture halls a sense of urgency. In Pakistan, the EI of special needs children is mostly unexplored and undervalued. There is a need to focus on this aspect of EI to work and after that, some studies have been conducted which are mentioned below to explore EI's importance in the special education sector (Mumtaz et al., 2021).

As a result, special educational institutions must pay attention to the teacher's and student's emotional growth in addition to their cognitive and technical development, despite its importance as a key component of overall personality development and, by extension, an important curricular goal, very little research has been conducted on the relationship between curricular activities and the development of Emotional Intelligence at the higher education level in the Pakistani context (Allal, 2020).

Research Objectives:

A rigorous literature survey will ascertain to meet the certain objectives to

1. Identify the role of EI among special education teachers in the existing literature.
2. Find out the relationship of EI intervention to enhance the EI among the teachers of special needs children
3. Explore the role of EI among the teachers of special needs children to enhance the positive change in the behaviour of special needs students
4. Evaluate the need for and importance of emotional intelligence of special needs teachers through a systematic literature review and provide the most valuable findings through secondary data sources based on the previous literature and studies

Research Questions

1. Is there any role of Emotional Intelligence among special education teachers?
2. Is there any relationship between EI interventions to enhance EI among the teachers of special needs children?
3. Is there any role of EI among special needs teachers to enhance the positive change in the behaviour of special needs students?

Research hypothesis

1. There will be a significant role of EI among special education teachers
2. There will be a positive relationship between EI intervention to enhance the EI among the teachers' special needs children
3. There will be a positive role of EI among the teachers of special needs children to enhance the positive change in behaviour of special needs students

Significance of the Research

Emotional intelligence is the capacity to understand one's own emotions as well as those of others, to use this understanding to control behaviour in accordance with interpersonal relationships, to boost the quality of life, to enhance mental health, to instil confidence in one's attitudes and others, to enhance empathy and communication skills, to win others' respect, and to be able to

quickly adapt to change and to able oneself and others to change in behaviour according to the situation in a positive way. The findings of this research indicated the role of emotional intelligence, the intervention of emotional intelligence and its impact on how teachers of special education institutes are involved in training their students of special needs children. As research suggested that the teachers of special education institutes need to pay more attention to their special needs students as compared to the general education teachers (Ghani & Zain, 2014). So, when we talk about Pakistan regarding EI, there is a lack of awareness related to emotional intelligence, so the current review of emotional intelligence will be helpful to enhance communication, quality of life, mental health, cognitive emotion regulations, and workplace issues among the teachers of special education. It will pave the foundation for future research in Pakistan.

Problem Statement

According to Chua (1976), the effectiveness of communication, positive mental health and commitment of special education teachers is a key component to train special needs, children. To comprehend the unique needs of special students, teachers of students with special needs must be stable to control their emotions intelligently. The world is growingly focusing on these issues, for example, numerous universities and educational institutions in Malaysia are providing special education teachers with training in EI (Ghani & Zain, 2014). Therefore, this area of research must be catered to in Pakistan regarding special education teacher training focusing on emotional intelligence among aspiring special education teachers. Consequently, it will improve the awareness and guidance programs regarding emotional intelligence focused among special education teachers.

Annexure A

Methods

The purpose of this review article is to identify and evaluate the relevant studies of Teachers' Emotional Intelligence among special needs children. In this regard, the current study is based on the qualitative approach focusing on the secondary data collection technique. In this regard, the data have been collected from various reliable sources. Journal articles and books are the major reliable sources under the empirical approach. Therefore, Google Scholar, PubMed, Science Direct, Research Gate, MDPI and ERIC have been used. Furthermore, these sources have been electronically used, and the most relevant sources have been selected through the set inclusion and exclusion criteria. The selected age for the teachers was 22-60 because in special education, it was the suitable range, and less than 22 age teachers were less experienced and excluded from the study, and data were searched with appropriate keywords, including Emotional Intelligence, Special Need Children, EI among Teachers and others mentioned below.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Concept of Emotional Intelligence

Gershon and Pellitteri (2018) stated that as a result of merging the concepts of emotion and intellect, literature arrives at the concept of Emotional Intelligence. The Latin root "mover," which means "to move," is replaced by the term "emotion." Additionally, the French word for emotion, emotion, comes from the word 'endeavour,' which means 'excite' in English. Strong emotion, such as happiness, rage, or grief, is what people mean when an individual says "excited." Emotional connections drive people to care deeply about their possessions. Smart, emotional management may help individuals find their life's calling and enrich people's trips along the way. People's emotions lead us to the best possible decisions (Harjanto & Sumarni, 2021). Emotion is defined as "a mental state that occurs spontaneously rather than via conscious effort and is typically accompanied

by physiological changes," including feelings of happiness, sadness, awe, anger, and love (Li, 2020).

According to Goleman (1985), an emotion includes "unique cognitions, psychological and bodily states, and a spectrum of inclinations to act." He went on to say that hundreds of emotions exist, each with its unique combinations, permutations, and subtleties. As for the definitions of the core emotions, he cited various studies before settling on a taxonomy of eight: anger, sorrow, fear, pleasure, love, surprise, disgust, and shame. The human's expressions of emotion are as varied as the stimuli they get from the world around them. Emotions, in a nutshell, are what set apart one's experiences of happiness, sadness, fear, rage, joy, love, and hatred. The emotions of humans help professionals to categorize the remarkable and startling times in individuals' lives (Sánchez-Álvarez et al., 2020). After defining the EI, there is a need to explore the historical changes and aspects of EI in detail which is given below.

Overview of EI

Sabie et al. (2020) stated that Emotional Intelligence is a relatively young field of study that has only gained attraction in the past two or three decades. Before 1990, the notion of EI was separate from intelligence study, and it wasn't given any attention by even the most eminent scientists, neuroscientists, psychologists, and researchers. Individuals with high levels of EI can monitor their own and other's emotional states and utilize this information to problem-solve and control their actions accordingly. In 1990, two books were popularised written by Western authors related to the concept of Emotional Intelligence (EI). They correctly identified EI in these books as the capacity to become attuned to and responsive to one's own and other people's emotional states, to differentiate between these states, and to utilize this knowledge to shape one's decisions and behaviour.

Bower et al. (2018) examined that over the years since, hundreds of teachers, parents, and academics have studied EI's potential applications. They also said that recognizing emotions, acting on them, comprehending them, and controlling them were all crucial components of Emotional Intelligence. In 1995, when Daniel Goleman (1995) released his ground-breaking book *Emotional Intelligence: Why It Can Matter More Than IQ*, the topic of EI was thrust into the spotlight. Emotional Intelligence, according to Freeman (1998), is the capability of knowing, understanding and choosing one's patterns of thought, action, and reflection. The ability to connect and one's own emotions are boosted by this. The learning process and methodology of an individual are characterized by this term. It's useful for organizing one's day-to-day tasks and setting priorities in life. Understanding what's best for others is at the heart of emotional Intelligence.

Mumtaz et al. (2021) investigated Pakistani universities and looked into the correlation between instructors' EI and their effectiveness in the classroom. The research was conducted using a sample size of 166 college professors from Central Punjab. Educator efficacy is significantly impacted by EI. EI is a more accurate predictor of high achievement at work among Pakistani secondary school teachers who are women. Malik (2018) evaluated that in Pakistan, pension and health benefits for teachers are seldom discussed or investigated. Several scholars have explored the relationship between emotional Intelligence (EI) and the success of university instructors in the classroom. To define EI, many scholars have looked at a wide range of issues, such as instructors' emotional intelligence and adaptability methods in higher education and teachers' ways of resolving interpersonal conflicts in the classroom. Teachers that have a high EI are more likely to enjoy their careers and achieve great levels of success in the classroom (Malik, 2018).

Elements of Emotional Intelligence

Numerous writers, each with their unique perspective, have classified the many components of Emotional Intelligence into distinct categories. Goleman (1985) broke down EI into two main categories: self-competences and social skills (other). Gardner's abilities of introspection and interaction further solidified this segmentation (Namyssova et al., 2019). Second, Goleman (1985) gave a nuanced breakdown of EI components such as emotional awareness and self-control. Over time, this model has evolved in response to the advice of subsequent studies. His work is an extension and development of the work of other academics who have pursued this line of inquiry to a greater or lesser extent; the notion of EI itself arose via many theoretical development phases (Harjanto & Sumarni, 2021). After discussing the elements of EI, there is a need to discuss the theories and foundations of EI which are the following.

Theories of Emotional Intelligence

(i) *Trait EI and Ability EI Theory*

Petrides (2018) investigated that Trait EI theory may be thought of as a collection of beliefs about oneself that develop out of more fundamental aspects of a person's character. Trait Emotional Intelligence (also known as trait emotional self-efficacy) is an aspect of Intelligence that focuses on how one thinks about and manages emotions (Potts, 2019). Ability EI theory is often referred to as cognitive-emotional ability, and it focuses on the cognitive skills associated with emotions (Mavilidi et al., 2021).

According to Li (2020), by acknowledging the individual nature of emotion, trait EI theory gives an operationalization of EI. Numerous theories, including psychoanalysis, humanism, social-cognitive psychology, and trait theory, have investigated the nature of personality as a unique combination of one's thoughts, emotions, and actions. Individuals may be distinguished from one another based on their traits, which are observable

tendencies or patterns of behaviour that define those (Hughes & Davidson, 2020). The Eysenck model of personality, for instance, elucidates two traits that are impacted by DNA: Contrasting characteristics of introversion and extroversion, as well as stability and instability. There are some models of EI, and the following is one of them in terms of personality factors and EI.

(ii) *The Big Five Personality Factor Model*

Buecker et al. (2020) stated that the "Big Five" or the "Five Factor Model," the Big Five Personality Factor Model is an experimentally developed model of personality that builds on the pioneering work of experts in the area. Five aspects of neuroticism, extroversion, openness, agreeableness, and conscientiousness are proposed. The term "extravert" refers to those who actively engage with the world, as opposed to those who sit back and observe it, while the term "openness" measures how receptive one is to new experiences, as opposed to how closed off one is to new ideas. Finally, conscientious people can rein in their urges, making it easier to complete activities and achieve other goals (Buecker et al., 2020).

Models of Emotional Intelligence

Kanesan and Fauzan (2019), examined that since the 1990s, Emotional Intelligence has been a popular topic of study. Being emotionally intelligent is referred to being aware of their own and other people's feelings and knowing how to regulate, channel, perceive, and master them in a variety of contexts. Although several theories and models have been proposed to explain EI and its effect on students' academic progress, only three models have received significant attention and scrutiny. In this field, Salovey, Mayer, and Goleman (1985) were the forerunners (MacIntyre et al., 2020). The 1990s saw the development of several theories that, among other things, attempted to define and explain the various facets of Emotional Intelligence. These models have been described in detail below to help in

getting a firm grasp on the EI idea (Kanesan & Fauzan, 2019).

i. Mental Ability Model

Mayer and Salovey's (1985) study of EQ as a concept led them to develop this performance-based model. Emotional Intelligence is defined in this framework as the capacity for rational self-examination through one's own emotional experiences. According to Mayer, Salovey, and Caruso (1985), Emotional Intelligence connects people's emotions to their rational thought processes (Ugoani, 2020). This theory emphasizes how cognitive abilities and affective states are intertwined. It outlined the steps one must take to improve his IQ by being aware of and processing feelings.

According to Valikhani et al. (2022), the Abilities Model is also known as the Four-Tier Model of Emotional Intelligence. The four-factor theory of EI is another name for the mental ability model. This paradigm breaks down emotional Intelligence into its parts, or "skills," which together account for the whole range of EI characteristics. Skills in emotion identification, emotion use, emotion understanding, and emotion regulation. The ability to recognize, understand, and regulate emotions is the domain of rationality, while the ability to effectively use emotions in service of one's thinking is the domain of Emotional Intelligence. Each of these four abilities has been broken out in further detail below (Valikhani et al., 2022).

ii. Recognition of an emotion

According to Chronaki et al. (2018), in this subfield of the ability model, Emotional Intelligence is defined as the degree to which a person is aware of and able to manage their own and other people's emotional states in socially appropriate ways. The ability to recognize and express a range of emotions, as well as to adapt one's expression of those feelings to the circumstances at hand. Emotional Intelligence is more than only the ability to read and convey feelings via words and body language, but also the ability to read

and convey the emotions of others (Mérida-López et al., 2020). The components of self-awareness and social awareness, such as feelings, body language, posture, and thoughts are important in this stage. It also includes being able to control one's emotions and act in a nonviolent manner. Following is the next step in this model to regulate EI.

iii. The utilization of an Emotion

In the study of Shao-Hua et al. (2020), emotional synthesis and problem-solving by emotional means are linked to this component of the mental ability paradigm. It includes the skills of identifying and analysing one's own and others' emotions, as well as the ability to articulate one's feelings and concerns. It also involves a realistic and attuned reflection of one's emotions in response to the feelings and ideas of others, as well as a positive frame of mind that helps one avoid stress. One's capacity to use emotions, emotional moods, and emotional states is reflected in the strength of the connection between one's ideas and feelings.

iii. Comprehension of an emotion

Berkum et al. (2019) examined that the capacity to recognize the progression from one stage of emotion to the next requires an appreciation of the nuances of individual feelings and the dynamics of emotional series. For example, when an unfair act happens in society, one may feel rage and a desire for vengeance against those responsible. It also required an awareness of the flow of feelings from one to the next. Dejection is a common result of unsuccessful endeavours; thus, it is important to know how to interpret individuals' feelings in context (Berkum et al., 2019).

iv. Supervising an emotion

Here, the capacity to use and regulate one's emotions, rather than being led by them, is emphasised. It also covers methods for acquiring wisdom and expanding one's mind to accomplish one's goals. Mayer (1985) maintained that the capacity to regulate one's emotions was the most crucial part of the

ability model and that doing so required both social awareness and self-knowledge. This competency reveals one's character via the skilful management of one's emotions. The most helpful part of the approach is the one that needs self-control, the capacity to help others, and the willingness to accept assistance from others. In a nutshell, it helps one become more socially adjusted and develop problem-solving skills. It is the last step in this model but there are some other important models of EI which are the following.

v. *Mixed models or Self-reported Models*

Multiple aspects of EI, such as IQ and personality traits, are accounted for in these models. Some researchers believe that the personality traits of empathy, openness, and sociability are included in the Self-Report models, which suggests that these models account for factors beyond intellectual capacity. It has been noted that mixed models and self-report models are distinct from one another. [Goleman's \(1985\)](#) model of emotional competencies, sometimes called his "Emotional Intelligence" model, is an example of a mixed-model approach to the study of emotional Intelligence, whereas the Bar model of Emotional Intelligence is an example of a self-report model. Moreover, the self-report model of EI incorporates the trait's practical side ([Key, 2021](#)).

vi. *Six Seconds Model of Emotional Intelligence*

The emotional competencies model developed by [Goleman \(1985\)](#) and the ability model developed by Mayer (1985) serve as the foundation for the "six seconds" approach. To put emotional intelligence (EQ) theory into practice for one's growth, one might look to the Six Seconds approach ([Kanesan & Fauzan, 2019](#)). Three facets make it possible for implementations to be put into practice. The Six Seconds model, which is simple and breaks down the eight EQ skills into three primary categories called "pursuits" (know yourself,

choose yourself, and provide for yourself), has been proposed.

Furthermore, [Chronaki et al. \(2018\)](#) stated that to better "know oneself" implies being aware of internal experiences. Two more subdomains fall under this category: detect patterns, which involves recognizing regularly repeating responses and behaviours, and improve emotional literacy, which involves effectively identifying and understanding both basic and complicated emotions.

[Buecker et al. \(2020\)](#) indicated that if a person makes a conscious decision to reply, then people are more deliberate. Among the four subdomains that make up this competency are the abilities to apply consequential thinking, that is, to consider the potential consequences of a decision and to navigate emotions, that is, to recognize, understand, and effectively use one's emotional responses as a powerful strategic resource. In addition, one practices optimism, which is having a proactive viewpoint of hope and possibilities and relies on intrinsic motivation, which implies getting energy from one's ideals and commitments rather than being pushed by external factors ([Buecker et al., 2020](#)).

According to [Key \(2021\)](#), two sub-domains fall under the umbrella of "empathy," one of which is the ability to recognize and correctly react to the feelings of others, and the other is the ability to pursue noble objectives by making decisions that are consistent with a larger, more meaningful life aim. Emotional regulation, self-awareness, and the ability to accurately assess one's feelings and the emotions of others to draw meaningful conclusions are all central to this framework ([Varea et. al., 2021](#)). Understanding and information regarding Emotional Intelligence are fostered by this paradigm, as are social and emotional learning, people's performance, and the ability to use this knowledge to create positive outcomes in their everyday lives. As mentioned all the detail is based on theoretical concepts, there is a need to explore the EI

importance and its implications in real life which are mentioned below in detail.

Need for Emotional Intelligence for Teaching Effectiveness

According to [Chen and Guo \(2021\)](#), third-world countries are at the lower point of the 21st century in the era of scientific development, and the ability to successfully navigate both internal and foreign threats will determine the standard of living enjoyed by its residents in this new era. Education is often seen as the best and most efficient tool for tackling problems like these. Successfully meeting the difficulties will need an education that is both meaningful and productive, one that takes into consideration the demands and ambitions of society as well as the individual's own physical and mental development ([Reeve & Shin, 2020](#)).

[Wajdi et al. \(2018\)](#) stated that today, it's more important than ever to help children grow intellectually but also to help them become contributing members of society by teaching them the kinds of social and emotional skills that will help them fit in and work along with others. However, people cannot expect a teacher to induce and nurture social and emotional abilities in their pupils if they lack such qualities. It is believed that they are the driving force behind these positive shifts in the way young people think and act ([Allal, 2020](#)). Only educated, competent, and caring teachers can develop the student's social cohesiveness, integration, and patriotism, which are the goals of the research. Based on the findings of this study, the child's time spent in the secondary level of school is crucial. This is an exciting time for the student since he has fresh opportunities and paths open to him ([Wajdi et al., 2018](#)).

The study of [Valente et al. \(2020\)](#) examined that a teacher must be successful in adequately educating his pupils for their future duties in light of the fast expansion and development of technology as well as other developing and growing difficulties. In this context, the teacher acts as a mentor who

encourages pupils to pursue meaningful careers. Since it's generally accepted that change comes from the ground up in neighbourhoods rather than from on high, this strategy emphasizes grassroots organizing in the special education system ([Valente et al., 2020](#)).

[Vesely-Maillefer and Saklofske \(2018\)](#) claimed that teachers are the true agents of social transformation; their words and actions have far-reaching consequences for their student's development. Further, they said, educators take on several hats during their careers, and they need to maintain a healthy mental and emotional state so they can do their jobs well. Possessing EI abilities may aid individuals in more effectively managing all these sources of stress. Due to its widespread prevalence, the concept of EI in the classroom is receiving a lot of focus and investigation ([Chen & Guo, 2021](#)).

According to [Kanesan and Fauzan \(2019\)](#), understanding one's own emotions as well as those of others around one, as well as learning to control such emotions, is a sign of Emotional Intelligence. Therefore, this skill is crucial for efficient education and must be acquired. Having a high level of EI helps people succeed in many areas of their lives. The entire literature has been abstracted from different sources and is a complete process of filtration. Following is the flow diagram that indicates the entire process to make this review more specific and systematic.

Findings and Discussion

This study has been based on the previous literature in the field of EI among the teacher of special needs children. There were thirty-five relevant studies, but all were not needed to include in the result section due to the similarity of concepts. There are ten studies that have been analysed through the systematic review, and findings are listed below in the tables and description of the tables. Further, these results are discussed in the discussion section of the investigation.

Annexure C

Table 4: Instruments Used in Measuring EI of Special Need Children

<i>Instrument</i>	<i>Total Studies</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
MSCIT	4	27%
ECI	4	27%
WLEIS	2	13.0%
EQ-i	3	20%
TEIQue	2	13.0%

It is indicated that there were five types of EI measurements that have been used in the ten studies in which MSCIT and ECI have been used more than half of the studies other three have 46% of the total studies used instruments. Based on these statistics and figures, it is stated that less used instruments in EI studies in the selected ten are WLEIS and TEIQue. WLEIS and TEIQue instruments have 13% of the total, and EQ-I has 20% of the total, which is a higher value compared to WLEIS and TEIQue.

Based on the literature matrix and previous studies on the EI of special education teachers, it has been seen that there is a significant role of teachers' EI in managing special needs children, understanding their emotions and enhancing their capacity to learn. There were mainly qualitative and quantitative approach-based studies that have provided valuable findings. In this regard, some studies have used mixed method study design, and data have been collected through

primary sources by using probability and non-random sampling. The matrix has all study's crux and findings that are helpful for future studies to develop interventions for special needs children to manage EI issues and enhance their learning.

The results suggest that special education' EI can be encouraged through EI training programmes that have the potential to bring about positive EI changes and associated behaviours that may have a beneficial influence on teachers of special needs children's practice of their feeling of meaningfulness, and their relationships with students. In this regard, most of the studies included in the matrix have supported the notion that teachers of special needs children are more likely to struggle for their improvements compared to normal children. There is a need for different EI measurements to evaluate the need and change of ability to learn more effectively. This systematic review and findings of the matrix evaluated that EI is a leading factor in special needs children for teachers to enhance the ability to manage special students, understand their attitude and manage them in a well-mannered approach.

Limitations

The current study is based on secondary sources, which is a limitation of the study. This systematic review is only applicable in the field of special education, and EI applications are limited to teachers of special needs children. Due to academic research and low budget, the current study has been completed under desk research, and much future research can overcome these limits by adopting the primary data collection approach.

Recommendations

The current study has focused on EI only in the aspect of special needs children and teachers, which is a more specific study in the field of EI. There is a need for more studies that can be investigated in the future to fill this research gap. The current study has systematically reviewed the 35 articles, and

ten studies have been discussed in the matrix in detail. This is not a limit. The. Future studies can review more studies and include more than ten articles in the matrix to make the study more vast and authentic. Furthermore, this article is based on secondary data sources and analysis, which may not follow the current trends in EI, but future studies through primary data collection methods can reduce this issue.

Conclusion

Emotional Intelligence has a great role in the special education sector in controlling special children, managing their class activities and keeping them on the right track. In this way, there is a need for emotionally strong special education children that can make the teachers of special education stronger and more effective in working better in the special education sector. It has been seen that teachers of special needs children who are emotionally not strong face many difficulties in controlling the behaviour of the children, but teachers with high EI are more likely to control and enhance the performance of children. So, it is concluded that EI is the main ability in special education to work in a stress-free and productive manner.

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Annexure A

Table:1 Review of EI Measures and Framework

<i>Measures Used for EI</i>	<i>Author (Developer)</i>	<i>Measurement Domain</i>	<i>Explanation</i>
<i>Mayer-Salovey-Caruso Emotional Intelligence Test (MSCEIT)</i>	Mayer & Salovey	Ability Domain	The individual must consent before scoring any of the 141 items included on this ability scale. Specific tasks are used to evaluate one's level of expertise in each of the subdomains that comprise emotional Intelligence.
<i>Bar-On Emotional Quotient Inventory (EQ-i)</i>	Bar-On	Trait Domain	This self-reported questionnaire has 133 questions, the answers to which are used to calculate an overall EQ score and scores for each of the model's five subscales.
<i>Trait Emotional Intelligence Questionnaire (TEIQue)</i>	Petrides	Trait Domain	The scoring method for this inventory is comprised of a total of 153 items distributed over 15 dimensions and 4 major categories.
<i>Wong And Law Emotional Intelligence Scale (WLEIS)</i>	Wong &Law	Ability Domain	A 16-item emotional intelligence measure is self-reported and has four components based on the ability model.
<i>Emotional Intelligence Scale (Schutte)</i>	Schutte et al.	Ability Domain	Emotional Intelligence (EI) can be measured by using the Schutte Self-Report Emotional Intelligence Test (SSEIT) 30 Items test, which is divided into four sub-scales (emotion perception, emotion use, managing self-relevant emotions, and managing others' emotions).

Annexure B

Table: 2 Research Strategy

<i>Databases</i>	Google Scholar, PubMed, Science Direct, Research Gate, MDPI and ERIC
<i>Search Keywords</i>	Emotional Intelligence, Special Need Children, EI among Teachers, Importance of EI, Role of EI in Special Education
<i>Limits</i>	All empirical journal articles. Written in the English language only
<i>Total Articles Found</i>	520
<i>Fully Read Articles</i>	35

Annexure C

Table: 5 Studies on Emotional Intelligence of the Teachers (Literature Matrix)

<i>Author</i>	<i>Sample</i>	<i>Research Design</i>	<i>Analysis Method</i>	<i>Main Findings</i>
(Dolev & Leshem, 2016).	26	Qualitative	Thematic Analysis	The results suggest that instructors' EI can be encouraged and that EI training programmes have the potential to bring about positive EI changes and associated behaviours that may have a beneficial influence on teachers of special needs children's practise their feeling of meaningfulness, and their relationships with students.
(Dolev & Leshem, 2017).	50	Mix Method	Regression and Thematic Analysis	The results show that trainees felt their EI skills, as described by the Bar-On model, improved because of the training course. Most of the special education teachers who took part incorporated the skills they learned into their sense of self as an individual, as a member of a team, and as a member of a larger organization.
(Zysberg et al., 2017).	1230 2209	Quantitative Cross-Sectional	SEM Analysis Correlation	The research found a weak but unfavourable correlation between burnout and job satisfaction among special education teachers. Specifically, the mediation hypothesis between EI and burnout was validated by SEM analysis. It discusses the findings in the context of the literature and theory around burnout and the idea of EI. The possible ramifications in cultural and organizational contexts are discussed.
(Nathanson et al., 2016).	150	Quantitative	Regression	Social interactions are important for teachers of special needs children to control emotions. EI is a leading factor in controlling and managing children in special needs school-level education.
(Colomeischi, 2015).	575	Quantitative	Correlation ANOVA T-Test	This study indicates the causes of special education teacher burnout and highlights the connection between burnout and variables such as EI and personality. The findings provide a picture of teacher burnout in Romania, revealing the primary internal variables that contribute to the problem.
(Latif et al., 2017).	210	Quantitative	T-test Multiple Regression Path Analysis	Path analysis and regression analysis both showed that EI was not a reliable predictor of future job success. Teachers of special education who scored higher on the EI scale reported being happier in their profession, and their kids performed better on standardized tests. In terms of teacher recruitment, training, performance, and professional development, this has significant ramifications for special

				educational authorities, school administrators, and teachers.
(Chandra, 2020).	94	Quantitative	Chi-square Analysis	The results showed that male and female special needs students differed significantly in their levels of anxiety about doing poorly in an academic setting, depending on whether they were at home or online. Many of them have begun engaging in new forms of artistic expression and attending educational programmes that teach them useful technical skills. Students were attempting to deal with the adverse impacts of the present pandemic crisis by employing emotional Intelligence and creating emotional distance from boredom and sad thoughts.
(MacCann et al., 2020).	42529 Articles	Secondary Quantitative	Meta-analysis	Variables that moderated the impact varied across the three types of EI. Ability Results in the humanities were more strongly correlated with EI than those in the sciences. A special need student's self-assessed EI was a more reliable indicator of academic success than standardized test results. Specifically, we hypothesis that (a) managing academic emotions, (b) forming positive social interactions at school, and (c) recognizing where EI and course material coincide are the processes that underpin the EI/academic performance association.
(Casas et al., 2015).	2806	Quantitative	Correlation and Regression	Whether a special education teacher was a bully or a victim of bullying, the results demonstrated a strong correlation between the two. Bullying engagement was also shown to be directly connected to EI. Not only that, but the findings also showed a clear correlation between teacher management and characteristic EI. Minor variances by educational cycle were discovered, but no significant differences by gender emerged from the data.
(Pérez-Fuentes et al., 2018).	2126	Quantitative	Regression and Correlation	Special education teachers who scored higher on the emotional intelligence exam also scored higher on the engagement test, suggesting that the interpersonal aspect is the most important predictor of involvement. Improving nurses' productivity in the workplace might benefit greatly from the findings of this research, which has important implications for practice.